

Death is Hard Work: Insolvent Violence and the Persistence of Literature

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A leading figure of contemporary Syrian literature, Khaled Khalifa has dedicated multiple novels to writing the repressed violences experienced by Syrian society under the Assad regime (1970-present). His most recent novel translated into English, *Death is Hard Work* (2016; translated by Leri Price, 2019), continues Khalifa's work of paying painstaking attention to how ordinary Syrians experience monumental historical events of displacement and loss, and how these events accumulate in individual lives and bodies, in families, and in Syrian society.

Death is Hard Work writes the ongoing war in Syria through three estranged siblings: Hussein, Fatima, and Bolbol (meaning nightingale), the novel's central character. A story of crossing Syria in a minibus over several days, the novel opens with the death of 'Abdel Latif, their father, whose dying wish is to be buried in the family village, Anabiya. The village lies outside Aleppo, and the journey of bringing the corpse to its burial site would, in ordinary times, have taken mere hours from Damascus, where the novel begins. Yet the mission to fulfill 'Abdel Latif's last wish instigates the novel's arduous plot. Checkpoints, conflict zones, shellings, and even the arrest of the corpse (along with its children) all slow them down. In the final pages, Khalifa is unflinching in his descriptions of the corpse's decomposition as the siblings race (if the verb can be used in the context of a war that has settled like lead over the hopes and desires of Syria's inhabitants) to reach Anabiya before it splits open. In the final scenes, Fatima, the least explored character of the three siblings, is struck mute by the horror of her father's rapid decay and infestation by maggots.

Brigitte Herremans contextualized Khalifa's work in a tradition of dissident literature in Syria, notably since the 1990s, citing the novelist's belief that literature's "response to dispossession is [the] strongest form of resistance [to] oppression." Khalifa, she explained, has remained in wartorn Syria due to his commitment to bearing witness to the war and to telling Syrians'

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stories in literature. Herremans noted the Libyan novelist Hisham Matar's commentary on the novel's title in translation, which suggested "labor" as an alternative to "work" that foregrounds the existential dimensions of the novel's task. Drawing on her interviews with the author, Herremans underscored Khalifa's refusal to write within the accepted categories and discourses of Syrian politics as well as to cultivate the empathy of his readers. He chooses an unheroic protagonist in *Bolbol*: an ordinary citizen, resentful of the regime's power but too afraid to act (most of the time). *Bolbol* fits the profile of a post-2011 category in Syrian politics and society: "the grey (al-ramadiyyin)." A sizable portion of the population, they refused to act with the revolutionaries and thus placed "systemic limits on the uprising" (Wedeen 22). As a result, the grey have been a target of opposition anger and mocking typologies in cultural production over the past decade (Wedeen 70-1).

In contrast, Khalifa centres *Bolbol*, a man plagued by ambivalence and weakness. With this choice, Khalifa brings into view what Herremans calls social violence: the quotidian slights and exclusions that preoccupy *Bolbol*, whose daily concerns – when he is not delivering his father's corpse across the country — focus on securing his neighbors' approval and living as invisibly as possible. This social violence intertwines with the military violence that is everywhere in the novel, breaking the siblings' journey, even besieging the spaces where characters find moments of temporary respite. Amidst so much abjection, we find in *Bolbol* a portrait of fear and isolation, but also of the most ordinary of hopes and desires. Herremans drew on writings by Hannah Arendt and Judith Butler to argue that these dimensions of the novel insist on the humanity and vulnerability of Syrian lives, too often obscured and dehumanized today.

The discussion that followed Herremans' comments was lively and multifaceted. Participants expressed their admiration for Khalifa's capacity to capture the dignity of his characters amidst degradation and destruction, as well as the ongoing meaning of rituals surrounding death. Khalifa's narrative thematizes the banalization of death in the war, with *Bolbol* grumbling to himself that in the presence of constant loss and annihilation, "rites and rituals meant nothing now [...] death wasn't even a source of distress anymore: it had become an escape much envied by the living" (6). "The Syrian war novel," states the late Hassan 'Abbas, "is a mass grave" (112). A pervasive, anonymizing violence even governs Khalifa's style. His earlier novel, *In Praise of Hatred* (2006), had marked the explosions of violence in 1980s Aleppo with sharp shifts in language and style. In contrast, *Death is Hard Work* lets death and loss to suffuse its

prose from beginning to end. In this context of relentless loss, the main characters repeatedly question the point of observing pieties around death, particularly when the journey exposes the siblings to so much danger. Hussein threatens to throw his father's corpse to wild dogs. Bolbol contemplates giving up and burying the body anywhere.

There are no moments of sentimental realization, no affirmations of filial duty to counterbalance the siblings' intense desires to abandon their task, to stop pretending there is any meaning in honoring their father's last wish. The novel and their journey simply continue. The siblings' movement across time and space, paralleling the linear movement of the novel itself, becomes a gesture of persistence — “a mode of living-on with the eternal dread of the present” — rather than progress, growth, or triumph (Berlant, 180). When the siblings finally reach Anabiya, the extended family is waiting and gives them refuge. They bury 'Abdel Latif in haste, but it is no source of catharsis or closure. They even neglect to bury him next to his sister, Layla, as the dying 'Abdel Latif had asked. What little relief that may be found lies in Bolbol's decision to scurry back to his dull existence — “like a large rat,” concludes the text — in the capital where he hopes to avoid regime scrutiny and the hatred of his neighbors — and above all, to sleep (144).

Very little can be recuperated from these closing scenes. Readers hoping for an uplifting celebration of the human spirit will be disappointed. Yet Khalifa is far from veering into nihilism. Resilience suffuses the text, exploding in expressions of love and childlike joy that seem anarchically out of place: 'Abdel Latif joins the revolution in his seventies and marries his childhood love. They frolic and kiss across the ruins of rebel territory as their aging bodies, like those of the younger rebels, slowly starve. The revolution assuages 'Abdel Latif's bitter disillusionment at the hollow promises of the 1960s — Arab nationalist glory, anti-colonialism, resistance to imperialism — in ways that appear unavailable to his son. This generational mapping of the 2011 revolution is a curious one in *Death is Hard Work*, as the protests and military rebellions in Syria were dominated by the young. Khalifa's choice implicitly suggests that Bolbol's life under the Assad dictatorship has robbed him of certain extremes in his political imagination and actions. His horizon stretches as far as making bargains with his surroundings to evade social violence and exclusion. Utopia is foreclosed. Only unrequited love permits Bolbol to glimpse other futures, perhaps precisely because they remain unrealized. He adores Lamia, a beacon of courage and solidarity in the novel whom we meet hosting and feeding displaced families with her husband, impervious to the dangers they face in welcoming

the state's opponents into their home. Bolbol muses that she gives him "the courage" to be otherwise, even reckless (53). Through Bolbol *Death is Hard Work* suggests, with Khalifa's characteristic compassion for human weakness and inconsistency, that we are not revolutionaries, brave, or for that matter grey in abstraction and isolation. Rather than "undivided selves," we are embedded in networks of social belonging, dependence, and recognition (Morales 86).

What is the fate of this entangled individual in a society that has been silenced, intimidated, and torn apart over decades, but most intensively in the past ten years? *Death is Hard Work*'s only reply is to offer nothing that resembles ordinary character development. This literary yardstick entered the discussion as a way to think about Bolbol's trajectory: had he changed by the end of the novel, asked the participants? On one hand, he sheds his nickname for his real name, Nabil, meaning "noble." On the other, he crawls into bed, "superfluous" and exhausted – hardly words that promises noble acts ahead (144). One discussant noted that despite the completed journey, much remains unfinished at the novel's deeply unsettling conclusion. If we are used to understanding plot as showing character development, whether in self-understanding or relationships with others, *Death is Hard Work* defies our expectations.

Something else accumulates along with the rot and maggots in the patriarch's corpse: an ambient trauma that tears subjectivities apart, silencing Fatima and deflating the brothers' dreams. Khalifa names this trauma, the offspring of decades of political oppression layered by the contemporary war, in a moment when the narrative muses on a figure of debts unpaid: "the shame and the silence they had lived through for years were exacting a price, and everyone would pay it, executioners and victims alike" (122).

Debts are relations. As narrative objects, they arrange time, causality, and ethics (Bouju). For Khalifa, these invisible bonds capture the proliferating, unnameable, perhaps even invisible trauma at the heart of this and his previous novels, accumulating in bodies and memory, soldering Syrians to one another in the very years of their most rancorous divisions. It is not that death and suffering form a currency for new relations between Syrians in the novel (or indeed for sympathy from the reader). In a passage that recurred in Herremans' discussion, a taxi driver laughs when he learns of the siblings' loss (8). Similarly, "the story of ['Abdel Latif's] body got no sympathy" from other displaced Syrians, numb and disinterested (48). Nor does Khalifa turn to debt to raise questions of settling accounts, a core topic of transitional

justice that is still postponed in Syria. The novel makes this clear through the ubiquitous presence of armed men at checkpoints, some driven by payback and profit, others by sympathy. The siblings narrowly escape the battles around checkpoints, waged increasingly by foreigners as the novel progresses, suggesting Syria has been engulfed by scores that may kill, but do not concern, ordinary Syrians.

Instead, Khalifa uses literature to gesture to the impossibility of paying back a price that won't stop growing for Syrians: too many losses, too dear to too many, accumulated over too much time. In this sense, *Death Is Hard Work* performs what Emmanuel Bouju terms a poetics of insolvency, with its persistent living-on figuring the necessary work of living, dying, and bearing witness amidst all that may never be settled. It is for this reason that the novel's plot is driven by a debt paid only partially (a debt, noted David Graeber, is a promise perverted by "math and violence"). The burial of 'Abdel Latif does not offer a full release for Bolbol (or, indeed, the novel), and his dying command is only partially fulfilled because he is not buried next to his sister Layla. Much as 'Abdel Latif's corpse invites its own reading as a symbol of the ravaged Syrian nation ('Abbas 123), Layla, a specter of the past and its patriarchal violence, asks to be read as the symbol of feminist revolt in Syria. When their father tried to force her into marriage decades earlier, Layla lit herself on fire on the roof of her wedding party, "a blazing torch [...] lighting the way for other women" (104). Yet another debt of insolvent violence, Layla's story resurfaces again and again. The family tries to bury it in multiplying stories, but her burning figure never collapses into ashes. In this sense, she is never fully dead, but nor can she or the resistance she embodies be reborn, triumphant and phoenix-like. Khalifa's decision to leave the siblings' corpses at a distance in the family land in the north, their wishes still unfulfilled, is thus a fitting end to *Death is Hard Work*. Although their corpses disappear into the earth, the siblings remain: lonely and irreconcilable symbols of promises squandered and debts unpayable around which new Syrian narratives will proliferate.

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